

Authorship and contribution guidance for the UKRN Open Research Programme

Authors and contributors

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Introduction

Authorship and recognition of contributions will be used to evaluate different aspects of the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) Open Research Programme (ORP), including how successfully we are sharing open research practices. Please familiarize yourself with this guidance, and consider carefully if you plan to do anything differently.

Requirements

Note the following are requirements which are explained in the document below.

- Do not use titles in author or contributor lists.
- Support contributors with name changes in a collegial and compassionate way.
- Apply agreed rules about authorship and contributions consistently.
- Do not gift authorship or omit authors for “strategic” purposes.
- Include the UKRN moderator account as an author in the OER Commons deposit (but not on the work or official citation) for technical purposes.
- All outputs must include authors and acknowledged contributors, as appropriate, we recommend the use of the [CRediT taxonomy](#) to support this.

Executive summary

This document outlines the authorship and contributor guidance for uploading materials, including, but not limited to: documentation; surveys; tools; and teaching resources (such as slide decks) (“resource”) created by the UKRN ORP into the sharing platform, OER Commons. The UKRN ORP defines an author as someone whose contribution has substantially impacted the final outcome of a resource. We recommend initiating early and frequent discussions on authorship within the framework of the [CRediT taxonomy](#). Collaboration and discussions should occur in line with the community code of conduct, and titles should not be included in author names. Additionally, when depositing a resource, we request that authors and other metadata about the output is clearly recorded. A sample cover sheet which describes and contextualizes the resource is provided in the appendix.

In this document

This document has been developed to support collaborators to have regular conversations about contributions to outputs and how they will be acknowledged. We respect that every project, work package, discipline etc. is different, so please use these as guidelines. Where there is a requirement, it is made clear in the section above and a rationale will be given in the text below.

Scope

This guidance covers all authored resources which are an output of the UKRN ORP, or resources which partner organisations wish to share alongside works arising from ORP. These may include, but are not limited to: documents, papers, slide decks, software, surveys, tools which support the uptake of open research and reproducible research practices. The chosen platform for sharing these outputs is the [UKRN OER Commons Hub](#). Outputs may be hosted, shared, or collaborated upon in other platforms, but we strongly advise that these works have a metadata record linking to the primary online location or describing the non-digital asset.

Guidance

Contributions and authorship

All contributions should be acknowledged. We recommend using the CRediT taxonomy to record all contributions. The Tenzing app can be used for this:

<https://rollercoaster.shinyapps.io/tenzing/>

Ensure you have regular and recurring conversations with all contributors about authorship and what is expected of authors. This ensures that deadlines are met, quality is assured, and the right people are accountable for their work, while also ensuring that contributions are rewarded and recognised appropriately. We recommend that there is a clear distinction between authors and contributors that is applied consistently, based on volume, mix, and types of contributions, regardless who the contributor is. Below, guidance is given on the difference between an author and a contributor.

An author is an individual who has made substantial contributions to the conceptual design or implementation of a project or work package which has resulted in the publication of an output (resource). Substantial contributions include, but are not limited to:

- conceptual or experimental design;
- product or software development;
- interpretation of results;
- proving/replicating results;
- contributing critically important intellectual content to drafts and revisions of a manuscript or an underpinning dataset which was created specifically to support that output.

Contributors who have not made substantial contributions to the conceptual design or implementation are not authors and may be acknowledged as a contributor. Contributions that warrant an acknowledgement, but do not warrant authorship status as isolated and limited contributions include, but are not limited to:

- proof-reading;
- technical and language editing;
- facilitating the peer-review process;
- administrative support for the underpinning project;
- actioning protocols;
- funding the project or acquiring the funds;
- leading or being a member of the research group that conducted the work;
- paid consultation or services*;
- data collection*;
- data processing*.

*Where these activities require additional intellectual contributions and are not instructed, they may warrant authorship.

In respect to the above, all authors should be able to identify their own contributions and are accountable for them. For an example, see the title page or Appendix 1.

Name changes

Co-authors and UKRN OER Commons Hub administrators must support contributors with name changes, as well as technology permits it, in a collegial and compassionate way. Name changes can occur for a variety of reasons, including changes in relationship status, religion, or gender identity. Unnecessarily inflexible approaches to author lists and metadata can prevent individuals from gaining the recognition they deserve. In OER Commons, authors and Hub administrators can make these changes to resources created in the Open Author tool, or in the metadata of other resources. For resources hosted on other platforms, it is the author's responsibility to make these changes.

Authorship lists should utilise [ORCID](#) persistent identifiers for clarity of author identity.

How to identify

Please respect how individuals prefer to identify themselves. However, if this does not use the latin alphabet, kindly provide an alternative in the latin alphabet. Where technology permits, the original name may also be displayed in its correct form.

Please do not include titles in author or contributor lists. If you follow this guidance, all authors and/or contributors will have made important intellectual contributions or have done substantial work and their qualifications and career progression (are important, but) are not the most important factor. Our Equality Impact Assessment (EIA) identified that when a mix of titles is used in authorship lists, people with protected characteristics are more likely to be overlooked. Therefore, we ask you not to use titles.

Versioning

Some published outputs are subject to versioning and remixing, for example, software, slide decks, policies, and guides. Indeed, OER Commons supports remixing in its Open Author tool.

Where versioning and remixing happens, any original substantial intellectual contributions as set out above should be acknowledged appropriately in each subsequent version. If a subsequent version lacks any contributions from a former author, that author may be removed from the authorship with all authors' agreement, but appropriate credit and citations should be given where necessary and in line with the licence under which the resource was shared. Note, including an original author or acknowledgement can be viewed as an endorsement of the remixed resource, thus all acknowledgements of contributions should be done with the full knowledge of the contributors. Also note, the authorship status (or lack thereof) does not preclude ownership or intellectual property contained in the versioned resource.

Technical guidance

Metadata, Cover sheets, and read me guidance

For written outputs arising directly from the Open Research Programme, a sample cover sheet is included in the appendix. For datasets, websites, software, practice-based or creative outputs, we request that a 'read me' is provided on the metadata record in OER Commons to provide the same information, in addition to details which will facilitate reuse, interoperability, and replicability.

The information should include the contribution made by each author and contributor using the CRediT taxonomy (<https://credit.niso.org/>). The Tenzing app can be used for this: <https://rollercoaster.shinyapps.io/tenzing/>

Example:

Title: Authorship and contribution guidance for the UKRN Open Research Programme

Authors: Anna Collins¹([0000-0002-6894-1697](#)), Lisa DeBruine²([0000-0002-7523-5539](#)),
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S.U.V. Resources: S.U.V. Supervision: S.U.V. Writing - original draft: S.U.V. Writing -
review & editing: A.C., L.D., E.G., A.H., E.R., L.S., and S.U.V.

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